

Estimation of heterosis for some traits in Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) in Central Uttar Pradesh

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on March 25, 2020 Revised on April 12, 2020 Accepted on April 24, 2020 Published on April 30, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Rishi Pal, Y. P. Malik Corresponding Author Email rishipal.biocontrol@gmail.com</p>	<p>The estimation of economic for parent heterosis <i>Linum usitatissimum</i> L. genotypes 11 characters namely, Flowering duration (Days), Bud length (mm), Bud width (mm), Sepal thickness (mm), Maturity period (Days), Dough stage bud fly infestation (%), Capsules/plant, Grains/ capsule, Yield/ plant (gm), Test weight (1000) grains and Oil content % were studied for testing the significance of differences among the treatments on experiment conducted at Oilseed Research Farm, Kalyanpur, of the university Kanpur during rabi 2012-13. The heterosis over economic parent (Neelum) showed positive and significant results. Crosses are JRF-5×Neela, GS-234 × IC-15888, GS-234 × JRF-5, EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234× Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neela, JRF-5×Shekhar, Shekhar×Neela and IC-15888×Neelum. sepal thickness, (JRF-5×Shekhar, JRF-5×Neelum and JRF-5×Neela). Days to maturity, (EC-1424× Shekhar). Dough stage bud fly infestation, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, IC-15888×Neelum, Shekhar×Neelum, IC-15888×JRF-5, GS-234×Neela, JRF-5×Neelum and Neelum×Neela. Capsule per plant, (GS-234×Shekhar, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neela and JRF-5 × Shekhar) Oil content and EC-1424×IC-15888, IC-15888×Neelum, JRF-5×Neelum, Shekhar× Neelum, IC-15888×JRF-5 and Neelum×Neela. for Seed yield per plant.</p>
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Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) belongs to the genus *Linum* of the family Linaceae. The somatic chromosome number of the cultivated species is $2n = 30$. It is cultivated for the main products fibre (flax fibre) and seed oil (linseed) or both (dual purpose linseed), but recently it has gained a new interest in the emerging market of functional food due to its high content of fatty acids, alpha linolenic acid (ALA), an essential Omega-3 fatty acid and lignin oligomers which constitute about 57 % of total fatty acids in linseed (Reddy *et al.*, 2013). World over, linseed is an important crop grown over 27.29 lakh ha with production of 25.2 lakh tons with average productivity of 923 kg/ ha, while national production of 1.525 lakh tons is from 3.226 lakh ha with low productivity of 473 kg/ha.

India still ranks third in terms of area after Canada and China, but slides down to fifth place in terms of production after Canada, China, USA and Ethiopia (AICRP, 2013). Average yield losses range between 19-98 %, 31-59% and 22-56% due to insect-pests (Srivastava, 1994, Malik, 1999, Patnaik and Lenka, 2000), weeds (Mani *et al.*, 1968 and Husain *et al.*, 2009) and diseases (Saharan, 1999), respectively. The significant yield losses occurs in linseed due to bud fly (*Dasyneura lini*) (20 to 97%), *Alternaria* blight (*Alternaria lini*) and powdery mildew (*Oidium lini*) (up to 60 %), (Srivastava *et al.*, 1997). Therefore, there is a need to develop varieties resistant to pests and diseases to stabilize the yield potentials of linseed varieties. Therefore, this research work helps in developing varieties resistant

to pest and diseases to stabilize the yield potentials of linseed varieties. The presence of non-additive genetic variance is the primary justification for initiating the hybrid breeding programme (Cockerham, 1961). Heterosis breeding is an important crop improvement method adopted in many crops all over the world.

It is a quick and convenient way of combining desirable characters which has assumed greater significance in the production of F₁ hybrids (Ramesh *et al.*, 2013, Jhajharia *et al.*, 2013). Several workers like (Singh *et al.*, 1987, Thakur *et al.*, 1987, Khorgade *et al.*, 1990, Khorgade *et al.*, 1993) have reported combining ability on seed yield and its attributing traits in linseed. Commercial exploitation of heterosis in linseed is regarded as a breakthrough in the field of linseed improvement for developing hybrids. Development of better hybrids using stable high yielding lines shall raise the yield of this crop. In order to achieve high yielding cross combination, it is essential to evaluate available promising diverse lines and their hybrid combinations for yield and yield components (Singh *et al.*, 2006).

The aim of heterosis analysis is to find out the best combination of crosses giving high degree of heterobeltiosis and characterization of hybrids for commercial exploitation. The studies of heterosis in linseed have also been reported by (Saraswat *et al.*, 1993, Foster *et al.*, 1998, Rede, 1999, Ratnaparkhi *et al.*, 2005, Sharma *et al.*, 2005, Reddy *et al.*, 2013). The commercial exploitation of heterosis led to the remarkable yield advances in several cross pollinated crops. In self pollinated crops, it is now well recognized that heterosis is very useful increasing productivity. Therefore, heterotic studies can provide the basis for the exploitation of valuable hybrid combinations in future breeding programs. In the present studies heterosis (mid-parent and better-parent) was estimated for seed yield and some important agronomic traits in F₁ generation of linseed genotypes using line x tester model suggested by (Kempthorne, 1957).

Materials and Methods

The experimental material included in present study consisting 49 genotypes comprising 7 parents and 21 F₁ and 21 F₂ was evaluated in a completely randomized block design with three replications. Each genotype was grown in paired row of 3 m length at a distance of 30×10 cm. The

experiment was sown on November 23, at Oilseed Research Farm, Kalyanpur, Kanpur, U.P. of the university during rabi 2012-13. Data were recorded randomly selected 5 plants/ replication were observed in genetic material., eleven traits *viz.*, days to 5% and 90% flowering, flowering duration, number of bud fly maggots/ 25 buds, bud fly infestation at green bud stage as well dough stage, bud shape (length and width), sepal thickness, flower colour, plant height, maturity period, capsule/ plant, seed/ capsule, test weight (g), seed yield/ plant and oil content (%). The data was subjected to analysis of variance according to (Panse and Sukhatme, 1954). The data were compiled and subjected to analysis of heterosis over economic parent according to (Kumar *et al.*, 2014).

Estimates of Heterosis

The heterosis was calculated (in per cent) as increase or decrease over economic parent (Neelum):

$$\text{Heterosis over economic parent (\%)} = \frac{\overline{F_1} - \overline{EP}}{\overline{EP}} \times 100$$

where,

$\overline{F_1}$ = mean value of F₁, \overline{EP} = mean value of the economic parent

Results and Discussion

The analysis of variance based on mean values of 11 characters namely, flowering duration (days), bud length (mm), bud width (mm), sepal thickness (mm), maturity period (days), dough stage bud fly infestation (%), capsules/ plant, grains/ capsule, yield/ plant (gm), test weight (1000) grains and oil content % were studied for testing the significance of differences among the treatments. The mean sum of squares for all the characters are presented in table 1 highly significant differences were recorded among all the treatments for all the 11 characters in both generations. The partitioning of treatments into parents and hybrids were also significant. Mean variances due to parents *viz* hybrid were also significant for majority of the characters. It indicated considerable variability with base material and material generated. The estimates of heterosis over respective economic parent (Neelum) in F₁ and F₂ generation for 11 characters were recorded and are presented in table 2 and results obtained for each characters are presented have

under: The estimates of heterosis over respective economic parent (Neelum) in F_1 and generation for 11 characters were recorded and are presented in table 2 results obtained for each characters are presented have under:

Flowering Duration

The range of heterosis over economic parents varies from -42.85 (3 crosses) JRF-5×Neela, JRF-5×Neelum and JRF-5×Shekhar to 3.19 Neelum×Neela. Out of 21 crosses, 17 were found significant and negative economic heterosis effects in EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×Shekhar, EC-1424×Neelum, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neelum, IC-15888×Neela, JRF-5×Shekhar, JRF-5×Neelum and JRF-5×Neela. No positive and significant was found heterosis over economic parents.

Bud Length

The range of economic heterosis varied from -23.66 (JRF-5×Neela) to 2.04 (Shekhar x Neelum). Out of 21 crosses eight cross showed negative significant economic heterosis crosses viz, EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, JRF-5×Neelum and JRF-5×Neela. No positive and significant was found heterosis over economic parent was found in hybrids.

Bud Width

The range of heterosis over economic parents varied from -27.39 (JRF-5×Neelum) to 10.13(EC-1424×Neela). Out of 21 crosses four crosses were found negative and significant. They were JRF-5×Neelum, IC-15888×Neela, EC-1424×Neela and GS-234×Neelum. None of the hybrids was found positive and significant.

Sepal Thickness

The range of heterosis over economic parents varied from 6.89 (EC-1424x Neelum) to 62.06 (JRF-5×Neela). Out of 21 crosses 14 crosses showed positive and significant heterosis crosses. They are JRF-5×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-

234×JRF-5, EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neela, JRF-5×Shekhar, Shekhar×Neela and IC-15888×Neelum.

Days to Maturity

The range of heterosis over economic parent are - 10.29 (GS - 234 × JRF - 5) to -0.73 (Neelum × Neela), respectively. Out of 21 crosses significant and negative economic heterosis was found in 17 crosses. They are EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Shekhar, EC-1424×Neelum, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neelum, IC-15888×Neela, Shekhar×Neelum, and Shekhar×Neela. The three crosses showed significant and positive for heterosis over economic parent (JRF-5×Shekhar, JRF-5×Neelum and JRF-5×Neela).

Dough Stage Bud Flies Infestation

The range of economic heterosis varied from -99.03 (EC-1424×JRF-5) to -72.67 (EC-1424×Neelum). Out of 21 crosses, 20 crosses showed negative significant economic heterosis in EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Neelum, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neelum, IC-15888×Neela, JRF-5×Shekhar, JRF-5×Neelum, JRF-5×Neela, Shekhar×Neelum, Shekhar×Neela and Neelum×Neela. Only one cross showed positive significant economic heterosis (EC-1424×Shekhar).

Capsule per Plant

The range of heterosis over economic parents varied from -3.84 (EC1424 ×GS-234) to 102.9 (EC-1424×IC-15888). Out of 21 crosses 8 crosses showed positive and significant heterosis. They are EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, IC-15888×Neelum, Shekhar×Neelum, IC-15888×JRF-5, GS-234×Neela, JRF-5×Neelum and Neelum×Neela. No significant and negative heterosis over economic parent was found.

Table 1. Mean squares for days to 50% flowering, plant height, capsules-1, branches plant-1, days to maturity, 1000 seed weight, yield per plant, bud fly (%) and *Alternaria* (%) in *Linum usitatissimum* L. genotypes

Sources of variation	Generation	D.F.	Flowering duration (Days)	Bud length (mm)	Bud width (mm)	Sepal thickness (mm)	Maturity period (Days)	Dough stage bud fly infestation %	Capsules/ plant	Grains/ capsule	Yield/ plant (gm)	Test weight (1000) grains	Oil content %
Replicates	F ₁	2	2.48	0.45	0.05	0.001	4.18	22.41	1000.33	0.107	5.40	0.05	0.54
	F ₂	2	4.62	0.06	0.25	0.001	5.58	10.00	207.46	0.012	3.24	0.31	1.82
Treatments	F ₁	27	25.14**	1.45**	0.31**	0.009**	129.28**	160.40**	4156.99**	2.791 **	19.82**	4.507 **	3.42**
	F ₂	27	25.29**	1.34**	0.56**	0.008 **	132.69**	169.86**	3193.71**	2.594 **	19.63**	4.65**	4.33**
Parents	F ₁	6	34.54**	3.12**	0.30*	0.02**	155.21**	437.10**	1084.89	2.714 **	10.11**	6.06 **	3.82*
	F ₁	20	22.40**	1.02**	0.31**	0.01**	126.93**	66.13**	2862.85**	2.938 **	14.54**	4.04 **	3.45**
Hybrids	F ₂	20	21.15**	0.87**	0.60**	0.01 **	132.36**	85.39**	1625.80**	2.354 **	9.93**	4.41**	4.69**
Parent Vs	F ₁	1	23.53*	0.05	0.53*	0.004*	20.57*	380.17**	48472.32**	0.321	183.8**	4.52 **	0.37
Hybrids	F ₂	1	52.48**	0.01	1.40*	0.001	4.06	250.56**	47204.77**	6.671 **	270.76**	0.80*	0.004
	F ₁	54	5.39	0.40	0.10	0.001	4.03	9.23	643.36	0.416	2.01	0.13	1.41
Error	F ₂	54	6.35	0.38	0.23	0.002	3.84	7.97	630.84	0.456	2.99	0.13	1.44

NB: * and ** Significant at 5% and 1% level of significance, respectively

Table 2. Estimates of heterosis (%) over economic parent of yield components in linseed

S.N.	Characters	Flowering duration (Days)	Bud length (mm)	Bud width (mm)	Sepal thickness (mm)	Maturity period (Days)	Dough stage bud fly infestation %	Capsules/ plant	Grains/ capsule	Yield/ plant (gm)	Test weight (1000) Grains	Oil content %
	Crosses F1	EH	EH	EH	EH	EH	EH	EH	EH	EH	EH	EH
1	EC-1424×GS-234	-38.09**	-21.72**	-11.50	48.27**	-3.18*	-79.17**	-3.84	0.00	-24.20	-37.89**	-0.14
2	EC-1424× IC-15888	-33.33**	-12.51*	-10.68	41.37**	-7.35**	-89.09**	102.9**	4.12	37.73*	-22.03**	4.20
3	EC-1424× JRF-5	-11.09	-17.97**	-16.98	41.37**	-2.94*	-99.03**	57.56**	-25.00**	-13.53	-42.32**	0.97
4	EC-1424× Shekhar	-28.57**	-2.84	10.13	13.79	-5.14**	72.67**	15.76	-12.50	-14.37	-31.10**	3.57
5	EC-1424× Neelum	-31.76**	-7.96	-5.20	6.89	-5.88**	-55.25 **	15.11	-20.87**	-14.27	-32.64**	-0.20
6	EC-1424× Neela	-36.52**	-12.51	-19.72**	31.03**	-5.14**	-84.54 **	28.30	-12.50	-4.86	-29.86**	-0.05
7	GS-234 × IC-15888	-38.09**	-4.89	-3.28	55.17**	-8.82**	-86.55 **	11.90	0.00	-1.26	-43.04**	4.35
8	GS-234 × JRF-5	-42.28**	-13.19*	-11.50	55.17**	-10.29**	-85.25 **	20.66	4.12	-4.75	-35.42**	1.49
9	GS-234 × Shekhar	-34.90**	-14.33*	-6.57	13.79	-8.82**	-67.44 **	37.95	-25.0**	2.64	-29.86**	8.26**
10	GS-234 × Neelum	-42.85**	-12.05*	-19.17*	6.89	-7.10**	-66.92 **	18.97	4.12	-4.54	-25.54**	-0.54
11	GS-234 × Neela	-38.09**	-8.30	0.00	37.93**	-9.31**	-76.60 **	77.50**	4.12	0.84	-33.05**	-0.05
12	IC-15888× JRF-5	-42.85**	-11.26	1.09	41.37**	-8.82**	-82.45 **	91.97**	-20.87**	51.16**	-16.88**	4.43
13	IC-15888× Shekhar	-33.33**	-6.71	-7.39	20.68*	-8.08**	-87.29 **	33.77	-4.12	14.16	-33.82**	9.56**
14	IC-15888× Neelum	-38.09**	-2.73	1.91	44.82**	-8.08**	-62.31 **	51.45*	-29.12**	30.33*	-8.03*	3.83
15	IC-15888× Neela	-42.85**	-4.32	-18.35*	31.03**	-8.08**	-76.01 **	2.57	-4.12	-10.46	-30.48**	7.37*
16	JRF-5× Shekhar	-19.04*	-8.19	-9.31	27.58*	2.69*	-73.56 **	36.02	4.12	-3.38	-46.65**	7.46**
17	JRF-5× Neelum	-19.04*	-16.49**	-27.39**	13.79	6.61**	-75.61 **	74.60**	8.37	28.64*	-27.70**	2.79
18	JRF-5× Neela	-19.04*	-23.66**	-9.58	62.06**	4.41**	-76.74 **	-0.95	-16.62*	5.81	-33.67**	2.62
19	Shekhar× Neelum	-12.71	2.04	-3.83	17.24	-8.08**	-48.59 **	45.02*	-8.37	51.90**	-9.88**	3.34
20	Shekhar× Neela	-12.71	-1.47	-7.39	20.68*	-6.86**	-70.64**	29.91	0.00	16.27	-11.22**	0.31
21	Neelum× Neela	3.19	-5.91	-17.26	10.34	-0.73	-50.52**	46.95*	-12.5	47.07**	-2.47	-1.41
	SE (d)	1.896	0.574	0.263	0.0256	1.642	2.480	20.710	0.526	1.157	0.288	0.963
	CD 5%	3.831	1.042	0.533	0.0516	3.318	5.012	41.855	1.046	2.338	0.582	1.963
	CD 1%	5.127	1.390	0.711	0.069	4.440	6.706	56.000	1.422	3.129	0.779	2.626

NB: * and ** Significant at 5% and 1% level of significance, respectively

Grain per Capsule

The heterosis over economic parent ranged from -29.12 (IC-15888×Neelum) to 8.37 (JRF-5×Neelum). The significant and negative economic heterosis were found EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Neelum, GS-234×Shekhar, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar and JRF-5×Neela. There were found no positive significant heterosis out of 21 crosses.

Seed Weight (1000 Grains)

The heterosis over economic parent varied from -46.65 (JRF-5×Shekhar) to -8.03 (IC-15888×Neelum). Out of 21 crosses 20 crosses were found significant and negative economic heterosis in EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Shekhar, EC-1424×Neelum, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neelum, IC-15888×Neela, JRF-5×Shekhar, JRF-5×Neelum, JRF-5×Neela and Shekhar×Neelum, Shekhar×Neela. Positive and significant heterosis was not found in any cross.

Oil Content

The heterosis over economic parent ranged from -0.54 (GS-234×Neelum) to 9.56 (IC-15888×Shekhar). Out of 21 crosses, only four crosses (GS-234×Shekhar, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neela and JRF-5×Shekhar) showed positive and significant heterosis. The significant and negative over economic heterosis was not found.

Seed Yield per Plant

The heterosis over economic parent ranged from -24.20 (EC-1424×GS-234) to 51.90 (Shekhar×Neelum). In all crosses, six cross showed positive and significant heterosis in EC-1424×IC-15888, IC-15888×Neelum, JRF-5×Neelum, Shekhar×Neelum, IC-15888×JRF-5 and Neelum×Neela. The significant and negative over economic heterosis was not found.

Heterotic response has often been expressed as a deviation of F_1 from the economic parental value (high yielding and well adopted cultivar) or superior parent. The degree of heterosis should preferably be measured as superiority of F_1 hybrids

over the best commercial variety. Such estimate, in real sense, decides whether the hybrid is worth exploiting or not. Accordingly, in the present study, heterosis was measured as direction of the performance of hybrids from the best commercial variety. The widely adopted and released variety Neelum was considered as an economic parent for estimation of heterosis for seed yield and other quantitative characters.

The degree and direction of heterosis response varied not only from character to character but also from cross to cross. In the present investigation, character shows dough stage bud fly infestation shows heterosis over superior parent ranged from -99.03 (EC-1424×JRF-5) to -48.59 (Shekhar×Neelum) in F_1 generation. Out of 21 crosses 20 crosses showed negative significant economic heterosis. The best five crosses are EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5 and IC-15888×Shekhar. Only one cross showed positive significant (EC-1424×Shekhar). In seed yield per plant shows the heterosis over economic parent ranged from 28.64 (JRF-5×Neelum) to 51.90 (Shekhar×Neelum) in F_1 generation. In all crosses, six cross as showed positive and significant heterosis. The best two crosses were observed (Shekhar×Neelum and IC-15888×JRF-5). Similar results were also reported by (Kumar and Singh, 2002).

In Flowering duration Character, out of 21 crosses 17 were found significant and negative economic heterosis in EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×Shekhar, EC-1424×Neelum, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neelum, IC-15888×Neela, JRF-5×Shekhar, JRF-5×Neelum and JRF-5×Neela. Similar results were also reported by (Sharma *et al.*, 2000).

In Bud length character, eight cross showed negative significant economic heterosis crosses are EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, JRF-5×Neelum and JRF-5×Neela. In sepal thickness character, 14 crosses showed positive and significant heterosis crosses are JRF-5×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5, EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neela, JRF-

5×Shekhar, Shekhar×Neela and IC-15888×Neelum. In days to maturity character, significant and negative economic heterosis was found in 17 crosses EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Shekhar, EC-1424×Neelum, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neelum, IC-15888×Neela, Shekhar×Neelum, and Shekhar×Neela. Similar results were also reported by (Sharma *et al.*, 2005).

In Capsule/plant character, 8 crosses showed positive and significant heterosis are EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, IC-15888×Neelum, Shekhar×Neelum, IC-15888×JRF-5, GS-234×Neela, JRF-5×Neelum and Neelum×Neela. Two crosses (EC-1424×GS-234 and IC-15888×Neela) were observed significant and desirable results were also reported by (Kusalkar *et al.*, 2002 and Kumar and Singh, 2002). In grain per capsule character, the significant and negative economic heterosis were found EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Neelum, GS-234×Shekhar, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar and JRF-5×Neela. Similar results were also reported by (Singh *et al.*, 2005).

In 1000-seed weight, 20 crosses were found significant and negative economic heterosis in EC-1424×GS-234, EC-1424×IC-15888, EC-1424×JRF-5, EC-1424×Shekhar, EC-1424×Neelum, EC-1424×Neela, GS-234×IC-15888, GS-234×JRF-5, GS-234×Shekhar, GS-234×Neelum, GS-234×Neela, IC-15888×JRF-5, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neelum, IC-15888×Neela, JRF-5×Shekhar, JRF-5×Neelum, JRF-5×Neela and Shekhar×Neelum, Shekhar×Neela. Similar results were also reported by (Sharma *et al.*, 2005). In oil content character, only four crosses (GS-234×Shekhar, IC-15888×Shekhar, IC-15888×Neela and JRF-5×Shekhar) showed positive and significant heterosis. Similar results were also reported by (Ratnaparkhi *et al.*, 2005 and Singh *et al.*, 2005).

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References

- Anonymous (2013) Annual report of Linseed: 2012-13, publ. project coordinating unit (Linseed), C. S. Azad University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur, *Executive Summary*, i.
- Husain, K., Bhatee, Y. N., Srivastava, R. L., Chandra, R., Malik, Y. P. and Dubey, S. D. (2009) Crop weed competition in linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L), *Journal of Oilseeds Research*, 26(Spl. Issue): 530-531.
- Kempthorne, O. (1957) An introduction to genetic statistics, *John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York*
- Kumar, M. and Singh, P. K. (2002) Heterosis in linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.), *Annals of Agricultural Research*, 23(3): 506-508.
- Kumar, S., Kumar, R., Kumar, S., Singh, H., Kumar, S and Singh, M. P. (2014) Estimation of heterosis in linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.), *International Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 10 (1): 356-359.
- Kusalkar, A. M., Patil, B. R., Thawari, S. B., Khatod, J. P. and Shivankar, R. S. (2002) Heterosis studies in linseed, *Journal of Soils and Crops*, 12(2): 196-198.
- Malik, Y. P. (1996) Assessment of economic threshold level of bud fly, *Dasyneura lini* Barnes in linseed, *Indian Journal of Entomology*, 58(2): 185-189.
- Mani, V. S., Gautam, K. C. and Chakraborty, T. K. (1968) Losses in crop yield in India due to weed growth, *PAN* (c), 14: 142-158.
- Panse, V. G. and P. V. Sukhatme (1967) Statistical method for agriculture research workers II edition, ICAR New Delhi.
- Patnaik, H. P. and Lenka, D. (2000) Damage potential of *Helicoverpa armigera* Hubner in linseed, *Indian Journal of Agriculture Sciences*, 70(3): 197-198.

- Ratnaparkhi, R. D., Dudhe, M. Y., Gawande, N. D., Bhongle, S. A. and Bhongle, S. A. (2005) Combining ability study in linseed through line x tester analysis, *Annals of Plant Physiology*, 19(1): 99-102.
- Saharan, G. S. and Saharan, M. S. (1999) Inheritance of resistance in linseed to powdery mildew (*Oidium lini*) disease, *Indian Phytopathology*, 52(1): 86-87.
- Sharma, R., Tiwari, S. K., Singh, P. and Kant Rama (2005) Heterobeltiosis and inbreeding depression in linseed, *Agricultural Science Digest*, 25(1): 35-37.
- Shrivastava, N., Katiyar, O. P., Das, S. B. and Shrivastava, S. (1994) Studies on evaluation of some germplasm line of linseed against bud fly (*Dasyneura lini* Barnes), *Geobios*, 21(2): 77-81.
- Singh, P., Singh, D. and Singh, S. K. (2005) Heterosis in relation to other genetic parameters in linseed, *Farm Science Journal*, 14(2): 1-3.
- Shrivastava, R. L., Jyothisingh, Karan Husain, Y. P. Malik, S. D., Dubey, J., Rai and Madhu Bajpai, (1997) Linseed: In: Efficient management of Dryland crops in India-oilseeds (Edited by R. P. Singh, P. S. Reddy, V. Kiresur), pp: 228-256.
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